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The Global Innovation Output Sub-Index

Decreased by 29.17% between 2013 and 2022

The Innovation Output Sub-Index is a fundamental indicator that measures the effectiveness of innovation processes within an economy, focusing on the tangible outcomes of a country's or region's innovative capacity. This index is based on a series of parameters that evaluate the number and quality of innovations produced, such as patents, scientific publications, new products and services, and their commercialization. Additionally, it considers the market impact of these innovations by assessing their diffusion and adoption both nationally and internationally. The Innovation Output Sub-Index reflects not only the ability to generate new ideas but also the skill to translate them into practical solutions that can contribute to economic growth and social well-being. A high value in this index indicates that a country is effective in transforming resources and investments in research and development into measurable results, such as increased business competitiveness and the creation of new job opportunities. Therefore, this indicator is essential for understanding not only the innovative potential of an economy but also its real and measurable impact on economic and social development. Its analysis provides valuable insights to policymakers, investors, and companies for making strategic decisions that can further enhance innovation capacity and long-term economic growth. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Innovation Output Sub-Index in 2022. The Innovation Output Sub-Index is a crucial indicator that measures how effectively countries transform their innovative capacities into concrete results, such as patents, scientific publications, new products, and services. The index provides a detailed overview of how well countries can translate innovative ideas into tangible outputs that can contribute to economic growth and social well-being. The 2022 data shows a significant disparity among countries in terms of innovation outcomes, reflecting different economic capacities, investments in research and development, and the presence of adequate infrastructures to support innovation. At the top of the ranking is Switzerland, with a score of 61.7, representing global excellence in converting innovation into tangible results. Switzerland has a well-developed innovation system, supported by a strong research and development ecosystem, close collaboration between the public and private sectors, and a favorable regulatory environment. This enables it to maintain a leadership position in the global innovation landscape. Following are Sweden (56.8) and the United Kingdom (55.8), both known for their robust research infrastructures and a culture that promotes collaboration between industry and academia. South Korea (54.9) and the United States (54.6) complete the top five, thanks to their advanced technological sectors and significant investments in research and development, allowing them to maintain high levels of innovative output. The Netherlands (53.7) and Germany (53.5) show similar results, highlighting the importance of advanced economies in Western Europe in producing innovation. These countries have highly industrialized economies with a long tradition of scientific and technological research. China (53.1) is a unique case, as it represents the only major emerging economy to appear in the upper part of the ranking. This result is the fruit of an enormous

government plan of investment in innovation and research, aimed at pushing the country toward a position of global technological leadership. Finland (49.3) and Denmark (49.1) show that even smaller countries can excel in innovative output thanks to a focused approach on education, research, and favorable government policies. France (49) follows closely, benefiting from its strong tradition in science and technology, supported by a high-level educational system and prestigious research institutions. Japan (45.8), despite being one of the most advanced economies in the world, shows a lower score than other developed countries, suggesting that it may face specific challenges in translating its technological capabilities into concrete innovative outputs. Malta (45.4) and Singapore (43.9) stand out as examples of small economies that have effectively leveraged their limited resources to create successful innovation ecosystems. Italy (43.3) and Israel (43.2) show comparable results, with Israel standing out for its dynamic startup sector and high concentration of research and development activities, while Italy benefits from a strong tradition in various industrial sectors. Moving down the ranking, we find countries like Iceland (43), Luxembourg (42.1), and Ireland (41.3), all characterized by relatively small but highly developed economies capable of maintaining good levels of innovative output. Cyprus (41.1) and Austria (40.7) confirm that even countries with limited resources can achieve significant results in terms of innovation through targeted policies and strategic investments. Lower down, we find countries like Estonia (39.7), Canada (39), and Belgium (38.5), which, despite being developed nations, show room for improvement in increasing their innovative output. Countries like Hong Kong (38.2) and Spain (37.4) follow closely, indicating that while they have good technological infrastructures, they may need further efforts to enhance their ability to translate innovation into concrete results. The Czech Republic (37.3), New Zealand (37.2), and Bulgaria (36.9) are examples of emerging economies that show a growing commitment to innovation but still face significant challenges to improve their position. Norway (36.9) and Portugal (35.7) demonstrate that even advanced countries may face structural obstacles that limit innovative output. Countries like Australia (35) and Turkey (34.5) show that despite efforts, there is still much to be done to increase their capacity to innovate effectively. Hungary (32.8), Slovenia (30.9), and Poland (30.8) illustrate the common challenges faced by Eastern European countries, which often struggle to bridge the gap with Western European countries in terms of innovative output. Asian countries such as Malaysia (29.4), Iran (29.2), and India (29.1) are examples of rapidly growing economies making progress in innovation but still facing significant obstacles in translating these advances into measurable outputs. Croatia (28.5) and Vietnam (28.4) represent countries in transition, seeking to increase their innovative potential through reforms and targeted investments. At the lower end of the ranking, we find countries like Latvia (28.3), Romania (27.7), and Thailand (27.6), which, despite showing progress, still need to overcome numerous obstacles to improve their position. The Slovak Republic (27.5), Moldova (26.9), and Lithuania (26.6) are examples of countries that, while having good potential, need more decisive policies to improve innovative output. Countries like Ukraine (26.4), Greece (26.1), and the Russian Federation (26) are at a disadvantage, often due to economic or political issues that hinder their ability to innovate effectively. Developing nations such as the Philippines (25.7), the United Arab Emirates (24.8), and Brazil (24.7) show that there is still much work to be done to translate their innovative potential into tangible outputs. Countries like Mexico (24.5), Morocco (24.4), and Chile (24.3) are at the lower end of the ranking, indicating that their economies still need to develop infrastructures and support systems that can facilitate better innovative output. Other countries like Serbia (23.7), Tunisia (22.8), and Jamaica (22.5) show that there is significant room for improvement to bridge the gap with more advanced countries. At the very bottom of the ranking, we find countries with severe deficiencies in the infrastructures and resources necessary to support innovation. Among these are nations such as Argentina (21.6), Belarus (21.4), Mongolia (21.3), Saudi Arabia (20.3), and Kuwait (20.2). These countries often face structural challenges that limit their ability to innovate and translate innovation into concrete results. Further

down the ranking are countries like Pakistan (19.5), Kenya (17.4), and Ghana (13.8), which face extremely difficult challenges related to poverty, lack of infrastructure, and political instability, severely hindering their ability to innovate. The lowest scores are associated with countries like Niger (5.3), Guinea (3.2), and Burundi (2.5), which are in a position of extreme economic and technological weakness, with very few resources dedicated to innovation and an almost non-existent output. In summary, the Innovation Output Sub-Index 2022 highlights the significant differences between countries in terms of their ability to generate innovative outputs. The results reflect not only the level of economic and technological development but also the effectiveness of government policies and investments in infrastructure and human resources. While some countries are global leaders in innovation, others face significant challenges to improve their innovative potential and translate it into concrete results that can contribute to economic growth and social well-being.

Innovation Output Sub-Index between 2013 and 2022. The Innovation Output Sub-Index represents an essential measure of countries' ability to translate innovation into tangible results, such as technological products, patents, and other forms of economic progress. The analysis of data between 2013 and 2022 shows a varied landscape, with countries that have significantly improved their performance and others that have seen a worrying decline in their results. Let's start with the countries that have shown the most significant improvements. Iran, with an absolute increase of 7 points and a growth of 31.53%, stands out as one of the countries with the most progress in terms of innovative output. This growth may be attributed to the country's efforts to strengthen the technological and scientific sectors, despite the economic and political challenges it faces. South Korea has continued to consolidate its position as one of the world's leaders in innovation, with an increase of 10.4 points, equal to 23.37%. This result reflects the country's heavy investments in research and development, advanced technological education, and government support for high-tech industries. China has also recorded a notable increase, with a 9-point rise and a 20.41% improvement in its score. This progress is consistent with China's strategy to become a global leader in key sectors such as artificial intelligence, renewable energy, and advanced technologies. Other countries that have seen significant growth include Japan (+4.2 points), the United States (+3.2 points), and France (+2.4 points). Although these countries already started from strong positions, their improvements indicate a further strengthening of their ability to translate innovation into concrete results. However, not all countries have seen growth; many, in fact, have experienced a decline in their scores, indicating a decrease in their ability to produce innovation. The case of Switzerland is particularly noteworthy: despite historically being one of the most innovative countries in the world, it has seen a 5-point decline in its score, equal to a 7.5% decrease. This could suggest that Switzerland is facing challenges in maintaining its leadership role in an increasingly competitive global context. Countries like the Netherlands (-4.4 points), Belgium (-7 points), and Denmark (-1.3 points) have all recorded significant declines, despite their historically strong position in the global innovation landscape. This decline could be due to various factors, including changes in government policies, reduced investments in research and development, or simply an increase in global competition. Another interesting case is that of Israel, which has seen a decline of 8.9 points, equal to 17.08%. Israel is known for its vibrant startup ecosystem and technological innovation, so this decline could reflect specific challenges or a slowdown in translating innovation into tangible outputs. New Zealand has also experienced a significant decline (-9 points, -19.48%), which may indicate a slowdown in the country's ability to leverage innovation to produce concrete economic results. This trend is also observable in other advanced countries such as Canada (-11.4 points, -22.62%) and Norway (-11 points, -22.96%). The case of Hong Kong is particularly significant, with a decline of 10 points, equal to a 20.75% decrease. This decline could be related to political turmoil and the growing influence of China, which may have hindered the region's ability to maintain its status as an innovation hub.

Emerging countries like India and Brazil have recorded decreases of 20.49% and 22.33%, respectively, highlighting the difficulties in keeping pace with more advanced economies in terms of innovative output. These score decreases may be related to factors such as a lack of sustained investments, structural problems, or political instability. The most drastic decreases have been observed in countries like Moldova (-15.7 points, -36.85%), Argentina (-15 points, -40.98%), and Kuwait (-20.4 points, -50.25%). These countries have faced significant difficulties in maintaining or improving their innovative capacity, which could be attributed to a mix of economic, political, and social problems. Countries like Venezuela and Yemen have seen the worst percentage declines, with Yemen experiencing a 43.92% decrease and Venezuela dropping even further, reflecting deep economic and political crises that have severely hindered their ability to innovate.

Economic Policies. To increase the value of the Innovation Output Index, governments must adopt a multidimensional approach that includes a combination of economic policies, structural reforms, targeted investments, and incentives to stimulate innovation effectively and sustainably. One of the first areas to address is the enhancement of the educational system, particularly in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields. High-quality education produces a competent and creative workforce capable of addressing future challenges. Governments should invest in educational programs that promote not only theoretical training but also the practical application of knowledge, encouraging research and innovation from the school and university levels. This could include partnerships between educational institutions and industries, internships, and joint research programs, as well as investments in school and university infrastructures to ensure access to cutting-edge tools and technologies. Simultaneously, it is crucial to improve the research and development (R&D) ecosystem through tax incentives and direct funding. Governments should create tax incentives for companies that invest in R&D, offering tax credits, allowances, and other forms of financial support. Additionally, they must ensure adequate public funding for research, especially in strategic areas that can have a significant impact on the economy. This could include funding research institutes, laboratories, and national technology initiatives, with the goal of stimulating innovation and fostering the birth of new technologies. Governments could also promote the creation of technology clusters and science parks, where companies, universities, and research centers can collaborate closely, share resources, and develop new ideas. Another key aspect is promoting collaboration between the public and private sectors. Economic policies should encourage public-private partnerships, fostering the sharing of knowledge and resources. This can be achieved through joint R&D programs, but also by creating open innovation platforms, where companies can collaborate with startups, universities, and research institutes. In this context, the government can play a facilitating role, connecting different entities and supporting innovation projects of particular relevance. It is also important to develop effective intellectual property protection mechanisms to ensure that companies and researchers are incentivized to innovate, knowing that their inventions will be adequately protected. A robust system of patents and copyrights is essential to ensure that investments in innovation yield an economic return for innovators. Another crucial point is access to funding for innovation. Economic policies must facilitate the access of companies, especially SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) and startups, to venture capital and the financing necessary to develop and commercialize new technologies. This could include the creation of public venture capital funds, state guarantees on innovation loans, and other forms of financial support. The government could also incentivize private investment in innovation through tax breaks for investors in startups and innovative companies. Moreover, it is essential to develop financial markets that favor innovation, facilitating access for innovative companies to capital sources through the stock market or other forms of financing. The regulatory context also plays a crucial role. Economic policies should focus on creating a regulatory environment that is favorable to innovation, reducing bureaucracy and

simplifying processes for innovative companies. This includes reviewing existing regulations to eliminate obstacles that may slow down innovation, such as outdated or overly restrictive rules. Additionally, governments should promote digitalization and the adoption of advanced technologies across all sectors of the economy through regulations that incentivize the use of new technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things. Introducing flexible and updated regulations that allow companies to experiment with new technologies without facing significant regulatory barriers is fundamental to stimulating innovation. Another key element is promoting the internationalization of innovation. Governments should facilitate access for innovative companies to international markets through trade agreements, participation in international research and innovation programs, and support for exporting innovative technologies. Economic policies should promote the integration of local companies into global value chains, facilitating cooperation with international partners and access to new technologies and skills. In this context, embassies and government agencies abroad can play a crucial role in identifying market opportunities and creating connections between national companies and foreign partners. Economic policies must also address the issue of sustainability and green innovation. In a world increasingly aware of environmental issues, policies should incentivize innovation that aims to reduce the environmental impact of economic activities. This could include incentives for companies developing clean technologies, investments in renewable energy, and support for circular economy projects. Sustainable innovation not only contributes to improving the value of the Innovation Output Index but also strengthens long-term economic resilience, preparing the economy for a future where environmental considerations will be increasingly relevant. Finally, it is essential to promote a culture of innovation at all levels of society. Governments must work to create an environment where innovation is valued and supported through awareness campaigns, innovation awards, and programs that stimulate creativity and entrepreneurship. Promoting a culture of innovation also involves supporting startups and entrepreneurs, facilitating access to resources, and creating a favorable ecosystem for innovation. Cities and regions can play an important role in this context, becoming innovation hubs through targeted local policies that support innovative initiatives and create spaces for meeting and collaboration among innovators. In conclusion, increasing the value of the Innovation Output Index requires an integrated strategy involving various sectors and levels of government. Economic policies must be aimed not only at stimulating innovation but also at creating the necessary conditions for it to translate into concrete and sustainable results. Investing in education, incentivizing research and development, improving access to financing, and promoting a favorable regulatory and cultural environment are all crucial elements for increasing a country's capacity to generate innovation and translate it into economic and social outputs that can be measured and appreciated globally.

Conclusions. The value of the Innovation Output Index decreased between 2013 and 2022 by an average of 29.17% for the countries considered. However, there are countries where the value of the Innovation Output Index has significantly increased between 2013 and 2022, such as Iran with +31.53%; South Korea with +23.37%, China with +20.41%, Japan with +10.10%, and the United States with 6.23%. However, there are also countries where the value of this variable has decreased significantly, such as Uganda with -78.36%, Mali -78.43%, Guinea Brunei with -87.97%, Brunei Darussalam with -88.93%, Benin -91.67%.

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Country	2022	Country	2022	Country	2022
Switzerland	61,7	Slovak Republic	27,5	Albania	13,6
Sweden	56,8	Moldova	26,9	Bangladesh	12,9
United Kingdom	55,8	Lithuania	26,6	Uzbekistan	12,8
Korea, Rep.	54,9	Ukraine	26,4	Dominican Republic	12,7
United States	54,6	Greece	26,1	Zimbabwe	12,3
Netherlands	53,7	Russian Federation	26	Botswana	11,2
Germany	53,5	Philippines	25,7	Guatemala	11,1
China	53,1	United Arab Emirates	24,8	El Salvador	11,1
Finland	49,3	Brazil	24,7	Kazakhstan	11
Denmark	49,1	Mexico	24,5	Ecuador	10,9
France	49	Mauritius	24,5	Tanzania	10,1
Japan	45,8	Morocco	24,4	Ethiopia	10
Malta	45,4	Chile	24,3	Tajikistan	9,7
Singapore	43,9	Serbia	23,7	Cambodia	9,6
Italy	43,3	Tunisia	22,8	Trinidad and Tobago	9,5
Israel	43,2	Jamaica	22,5	Myanmar	9,3
Iceland	43	South Africa	22,1	Senegal	8,9
Luxembourg	42,1	Argentina	21,6	Cote d'Ivoire	8,5
Ireland	41,3	Belarus	21,4	Kyrgyz Republic	8,4
Cyprus	41,1	Mongolia	21,3	Nigeria	8,4
Austria	40,7	Saudi Arabia	20,3	Yemen, Rep.	8,3
Estonia	39,7	Kuwait	20,2	Azerbaijan	7,6

Canada	39	Qatar	20,1	Nepal	7,6
Belgium	38,5	Sri Lanka	19,9	Nicaragua	7,4
Hong Kong SAR, China	38,2	Pakistan	19,5	Namibia	7,3
Spain	37,4	Colombia	19,2	Cameroon	7,2
Czechia	37,3	Costa Rica	19,1	Zambia	7,1
New Zealand	37,2	Montenegro	19,1	Honduras	7
Bulgaria	36,9	Armenia	18,9	Angola	6,8
Norway	36,9	Indonesia	18,8	Algeria	6,7
Portugal	35,7	Bosnia and Herzegovina	18,4	Mozambique	6,7
Australia	35	Uruguay	17,9	Mali	6,6
Turkiye	34,5	North Macedonia	17,7	Uganda	6,6
Hungary	32,8	Jordan	17,5	Lao PDR	6,1
Slovenia	30,9	Kenya	17,4	Rwanda	5,8
Poland	30,8	Panama	17,3	Burkina Faso	5,4
Malaysia	29,4	Peru	16,6	Togo	5,4
Iran, Islamic Rep.	29,2	Egypt, Arab Rep.	16,2	Niger	5,3
India	29,1	Georgia	16,2	Guinea	3,2
Croatia	28,5	Paraguay	14,5	Iraq	3,2
Vietnam	28,4	Bahrain	14,3	Brunei Darussalam	3,1
Latvia	28,3	Madagascar	14,3	Burundi	2,5
Romania	27,7	Oman	14,1	Benin	1,7
Thailand	27,6	Ghana	13,8	Mauritania	1,1

